

THE EXPRESSION OF NATURE'S RELATION TO SOCIETY IN HAMZA IMANBERDIYEV'S POEMS

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Abstract. The article analyzes plot poems written by children's poets. It is revealed that through the metaphorical expression of birds, animals, animals in children's poems, thoughts are expressed about current ecological problems, thereby the goal of changing the attitude towards nature, birds, and the biosphere in general in the minds of the young generation is aimed at a positive direction.

Key words: nature, ecology, animals, birds, living nature, metaphor, metaphor, plot, allegory, symbol, composition, character.

Children feel what adults feel. But in order to write poems that educate the thinking of young readers, it is necessary to find the dreams in the hearts of children, to be interested in the things that interest them, to be surprised by the things that amaze them.

Children perceive the world in their own way. In fact, things that seem simple to us look tragic in their eyes, painful and dreamy to adults, insoluble problems can be found in their eyes with a simple solution.

Hamza Imonberdiyev, a talented children's poet, is distinguished by the fact that he carefully notices these aspects and can reflect their world to himself. The world of themes of the poet's works is diverse, the content is wide, and the artistic level is high. The difference between H. Imonberdiyev and other children's poets is in his upbringing as a philosopher. In each small work, he teaches his young readers something, invites them to live by drawing conclusions from their life experiences. H. Imonberdiyev writes many thoughtful and philosophical poems with broad observations, in addition to speaking to children's hearts. It encourages children to think about the wonders of the world, current social problems in life, political events, human rights, freedom and freedom. The poet's poems play an important role in the development of the child's thinking, in understanding the animals, trees, colorful world, various flowers and birds, and the closest loved ones.

The artistic expression in the poet's poems is mostly passed through the prism of the mind. It is also the art of being able to express complex relationships to little ones. The author always approaches reality as a child's imagination, and uses mature thinking in interpreting them. In summing up, he demonstrates the skill of education. Also, the words arranged in H.

Imonberdiyev's poetic verses tighten the reins of the delicate feelings of the child's heart and lead to new discoveries. In the poet's poems, feelings such as love, longing, dreams, regret, hatred in the heart of a child serve as the main motive.

For example, in the poem "Mother Island" a huge socio-political idea is interpreted through concepts close to children's thinking.

*Bolajonim Amu, Sir
O'ynab qoldi qaydadir
Ko'p sog'indim ichikdim
Nega ular kechikdi .*

Even in the first lines of the poem, the style suitable for children's spirit and taste is visible. The poet draws a scene that is very familiar and close to the world of children to describe water, which is considered the source of life, and its value, and at the same time, the tragedies that caused the destruction of the ecological environment in Uzbekistan through the cry of Mother Island. Amu and Sir are happy, playful twin boys who seem to be filling their mother's bosom. But they are "playing somewhere" and that's why mother Arol complains:

*Bag'rim qoldi huvillab,
Sur shamollar guvillab,
Ko'zimga qum purkaydi,
Bir lahza jim tursaydi.*

It is known that the one and only sea that ensures the stability of our beautiful country is Arol. Amudarya and Syrdarya regularly poured their water into it. Only in the last 50-60 years has this natural process been interrupted. It is known that the reason for this is that the development of gray and protected lands during the period of the sole administration of cotton led to a sharp decrease in the water of these two rivers, as a result of which the Aral Sea dried up and affected the ecological environment of the oasis.

Although the negative impact of the event is clearly understood by adults, it is natural that today's young generation does not immediately understand this tragedy, has no idea about it. therefore, the poet describes in it a feeling very close to the heart of all children - the relationship between mother and child, especially in the form of their separation pain. As a result, mother Arol misses "her sons", mourns and breaks down, but does not lose hope:

*Kuta-kuta toldim-ku,
E, voh, cho'kib qoldim-ku.
To'ldirsa deb bag'rimni,*

*Olishsa deb dardimni,
Umid bilan kutyapman,
Yoshim ichga yutyapman.
Bergan sutimni oqlab,
Kelib qoladi o'ynoqlab.*

In this way, the poet succeeds in instilling in the young generation the sense of confidence in the restoration of the ecological condition of the country and positive changes. It also serves to educate young people in the spirit that by appreciating water, they can help the Mother Island by conserving it. "Our literature," wrote the poet Amon Matjon, "is closely connected with our history." Aruz writes the history of our nation, and poetry is his song.

So to speak, H. Imonberdiyev's poems are songs that create such a historical reality in children's poetry. People say: if you spit in the sky, your spit will splash on your face; there are sayings that if you dig deep for someone, you are comfortable with him. Many stories and legends have been created in this regard. Hamza Imonberdiyev's poem "O'q" is written under the influence of such narrations and is referred to young readers. An arrow fired from a bow does not know if it will hit in life. The bullet doesn't look down on anyone, it moves forward saying that I will destroy the Tsar's side, I will shoot him, I will kill his heart. It's like saying that "sucking is the job of a snake to spew poison." The poet animates the "bullet" and the object and animal he encounters. A phenomenon that seems abstract to children appears in a familiar scene.

In the poet's poem "Kangaroo's Call", the fate of the kangaroo in the zoo, the fact that he missed his child who was left far away when he got old, even though he spent his life in this cage, his heart couldn't bear it anymore, he lamented. the story is told. Even tears rolled down from the animal's eyes: "I beg you, my dear, open your cage as soon as possible!" there is vitality in saying.

Logical thought in such poems is clearly understood as a tragic fate of lack of free will. If you pay attention, the system of events and images chosen by the poet is unique. In addition, it is well known to the children that the animals in the zoo, including the kangaroo, are the homeland of Australia, and that it is the fastest running animal in the world. It is also a familiar sight that the quail is flying around the wide meadows and fields, gracefully walking in its own nature and freedom. Not only adults, but also children and teenagers can imagine the condition of these animals in cages and captivity.

The important thing is that until that time, our literature, including children's poetry, mainly expressed the attitude of society, that is children,

towards nature, animals and plants. In the children's literature of the period of independence, the opposite of this attitude, that is, the appeal of nature to humanity, the word "say" has increased. Our poets express the laws of nature by embodying the image of various plants and trees, rivers and seas, animals and birds, and deeply researching their world. The environmental problems that are occurring all over the world require this. Therefore, it can be said that the work of H.Imonberdiyev is the most observed in this interpretation. the symbolic images of the poet actually carry this motive.

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